

Volumetric Texture Analysis for Unsupervised Ink Detection in Herculaneum Papyri

Oleksandr Korotetskyi^{1,2} and Michal Haindl²

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20766169>

Abstract

The Herculaneum papyri, carbonised by the 79 AD eruption of Mount Vesuvius, can be imaged by X-ray micro-CT, yet their carbon-based ink is nearly iso-attenuating with the carbonised substrate and usually leaves no high contrast in the reconstructed volume. State-of-the-art ink readers are supervised neural networks trained against labour-intensive labels and tuned on cropped regions of each segment; their letter-by-letter legibility is uneven and they offer little explainability. Motivated by the community's call for a clearer understanding of the patterns underlying ink detection, we present a deterministic, training-free alternative that treats the unwrapped depth slab as a genuine 3-D signal. Three established texture descriptors — first-order statistics, Laws' texture energy and block spatial autocorrelation — are lifted to volumetric form and evaluated both individually as stand-alone ink responses and jointly as a per-voxel mean fusion; the resulting volumetric response is projected to 2-D under a per-specimen depth prior, smoothed by a soft Markov random field and binarised at an adaptive per-specimen threshold. Across 25 manually annotated Greek-letter specimens of Scroll 5 (PHerc. 172), under a δ -pixel exclusion band around the ink-mask contour, the best single descriptor reaches a mean Matthews correlation coefficient (MCC) of 0.374, strictly positive on every specimen. Run on the full segment, the same operator also surfaces partially recognisable text whose letters match the community ink-prediction of a *neighbouring* segment that overlaps with the analysed segment in volume. The pipeline is thus offered as a deterministic, explainable complementary signal that, in favourable cases, supervised neural detectors may consume as an additional input or weak label.

Keywords: Herculaneum papyri, PHerc. 172, X-ray micro-CT, unsupervised ink detection, volumetric texture analysis, 3-D block autocorrelation, 3-D Laws' texture energy, 3-D first-order statistics, peak-anchored normal depth prior, soft Markov random field, adaptive threshold, per-voxel evidence map, Vesuvius Challenge

¹Faculty of Information Technology, Czech Technical University in Prague, Thákurova 9, 160 00 Prague 6, Czech Republic, ²Institute of Information Theory and Automation, Czech Academy of Sciences, Pod Vodárenskou věží 4, 182 08 Prague 8, Czech Republic

Correspondence

korotole@cvut.cz, haindl@utia.cas.cz

1. Introduction

2
3 The Herculaneum scrolls – approximately 1 800 papyrus rolls excavated in 1752 from the
4 Villa of the Papyri and carbonised by the pyroclastic surge that accompanied the 79 AD eruption
5 of Mount Vesuvius – are too brittle to unroll physically (Fig. 1). Each sheet is itself a two-layer
6 composite: a *recto* side with horizontal fibres and a *verso* side with vertical fibres laid on top of
7 each other (Vesuvius Challenge organizers, 2023); the rolled scroll therefore exhibits an alternat-
8 ing horizontal/vertical fibre pattern between successive wraps in the μ CT volume, and ink sits
9 as a thin layer on the *recto* surface.

Figure 1 – Carbonised Herculaneum papyrus scrolls, images courtesy of the Vesuvius Challenge (Handmer et al., 2023; Vesuvius Challenge, 2025b). Left: photograph with a 15-cm ruler for scale. Right: exemplary internal structure revealed by X-ray micro-CT, showing the tightly wrapped papyrus laminae.

10 Modern μ CT scanning, combined with virtual unwrapping (Seales et al., 2016), provides a
11 non-invasive route to the underlying text: the scanned volume is segmented into a thin sheet
12 that follows the papyrus surface and re-projected as a stack of co-registered depth layers. The
13 remaining and dominant difficulty is *ink detection*: the iron-free, soot-and-gum carbon ink used
14 in the first century has nearly the same X-ray attenuation as the carbonised substrate, so direct
15 intensity thresholding is error-prone.

16 The community-driven *Vesuvius Challenge*¹ has accelerated progress on this problem with a
17 series of supervised deep models that have recovered legible Greek text from previously unread-
18 able scrolls (Farritor, 2023; Friedman et al., 2023, 2024; Nader, 2023; Roth and Nowak, 2025). A
19 structural drawback of the supervised paradigm remains: the trained models are opaque – the
20 patterns they exploit are not yet understood – their letter legibility is uneven across glyphs, they
21 depend on scarce labour-intensive ground truth, and they have yet to be scaled from cropped
22 regions to whole scrolls (Vesuvius Challenge, 2025a).

23 We investigate whether established texture-analysis methods, lifted into 3-D, retain method-
24 ological relevance for volumetric ink detection. We treat the unwrapped depth slab as a genuine
25 3-D signal and let every per-voxel descriptor act in 3-D, so that stroke continuity across the
26 z-axis is captured directly inside the operator support.

27 We make the following contributions:

¹<https://scrollprize.org>; the EduceLab-Scrolls dataset (Parsons et al., 2023) is the publicly released subset on which the work below is performed.

- 28 (1) **Peak-anchored normal depth prior.** A peak-driven envelope clipped to the surround-
29 ing mean-curve local minima intensifies the operator response inside the depth window
30 where the ink signal is most concentrated – relevant where segment volumes overlap
31 and several papyrus sheets coexist within the same crop (Section 4.3).
- 32 (2) **Volumetric texture descriptors.** Three well-established pixel-level operators (Haralick,
33 1979; Haralick et al., 1973; Laws, 1980) are lifted to act in 3-D, so that ink-stroke conti-
34 nuity along the z-axis is captured within each operator’s own support (Section 4.4).
- 35 (3) **Per-specimen adaptive threshold.** An upper-tail offset of each prediction’s own intensity
36 statistics, accommodates the between-specimen drift of the prediction-intensity distri-
37 bution without manual tuning (Section 4.5).

38 This work aims at contributing to several sub-problems of the community-curated open
39 ink-detection agenda (Vesuvius Challenge, 2025a) – whole-segment application, interpretable
40 voxel-level patterns and training-free maps that can serve as input or weak labels for supervised
41 pipelines.

42 2. Related work

43 **Virtual unwrapping and Herculaneum imaging.** The virtual-unwrapping pipeline of Seales et al.
44 (Seales et al., 2016) is the methodological ancestor of the Vesuvius Challenge: it produced the
45 first computer-assisted reading of an intact scroll (the *En-Gedi* biblical fragment). Mocella et al.
46 (Mocella et al., 2015) reported that X-ray phase-contrast imaging recovers individual letters in-
47 side rolled Herculaneum fragments. The Educelab-Scrolls dataset (Parsons et al., 2023) provides
48 the public scroll volumes, surface meshes and depth-layer renderings on which our work and
49 the wider community operate. The geometric difficulty of Herculaneum imaging is exemplified
50 by Henderson (Henderson, 2025), who illustrates how the compressed and distorted spiral of
51 *PHerc. Paris 4* and the breaks and falsely-joined sheets of current automatic segmentations stand
52 apart from earlier unwrapping benchmarks on simpler targets – folded papyri or documents with
53 well-spaced windings (Klenert et al., 2025; Kulagin et al., 2024; Mahnke et al., 2020; Polevoy et
54 al., 2022). Our paper is downstream of segmentation: we operate on the depth-layer stack of a
55 region for which a ground-truth surface mesh has already been produced and a flattened $Z \times Y \times X$
56 slab is available, and we focus on extracting the ink signal inside that slab.

57 **Deep ink detection in the Vesuvius Challenge.** The Vesuvius Challenge organised the supervised
58 deep-learning effort on the Herculaneum corpus around three annual cycles. The 2023 Grand-
59 Prize submission by Nader, Farritor and Schilliger (Friedman et al., 2023; Nader et al., 2024)
60 fixed the canonical recipe (Fig. 2) – a video-style transformer (TimeSformer) backbone trained
61 against IR-derived labels and ensembled with a 3-D ResNet-101 and an I3D head – and recover-
62 ed the first sustained passages of Greek text from Scroll 1. The 2024 cycle (Friedman et al.,
63 2024) concentrated on *automating* the surrounding pipeline rather than replacing the underly-
64 ing detection backbone. In 2025 the focus shifted to PHerc. 172 (Scroll 5), the same data on
65 which the present article operates: by early 2026 about 70% of Scroll 5 had been digitally un-
66 wrapped (Vesuvius Challenge Team, 2025, 2026), and the \$60 000 First Title Prize was awarded
67 to Roth and Nowak for recovering the work’s title from inside the still-rolled scroll using a cus-
68 tom MiniUNETR architecture (Roth and Nowak, 2025). Scroll 5’s ink is reported unusually dense
69 and exhibits plate-like surfaces shared with Scroll 4, tantalizingly similar to Scroll 1’s “crackle”

70 feature (Vesuvius Challenge Team, 2025), motivating training-free baselines that do not depend
 71 on scroll-specific labelled volumes.

Figure 2 – Supervised ink-detection paradigm of the Vesuvius Challenge. A flattened papyrus fragment (a) is imaged in two modalities: an X-ray micro-CT volume (b) from which a virtually unwrapped surface mesh (c) is extracted (magenta), and an infrared photograph (e) of the same physical fragment. A detector is trained on paired patches: the input (d) is the $W \times H \times D$ slab of surface voxels around the mesh in (c); the supervisory label (g) is the binary ink mask obtained by thresholding the registered IR photograph (f). Our work bypasses this label-acquisition path entirely and operates only on inputs of the form (d). Image reproduced from the Vesuvius Challenge tutorial materials (Vesuvius Challenge, 2025a).

72 **Volumetric segmentation tooling.** The Vesuvius Challenge ecosystem authors segmentations
 73 through domain-specific desktop tools built on the EduceLab `.volpkg` layout: Volume Cartog-
 74 rapher (VC) (Parker and EduceLab, 2016) and its maintained fork VC3D (Schilling et al., 2025).
 75 Crackle Viewer (Schilliger, 2023) is the companion ink-labelling tool presented alongside Thau-
 76 mato Anakalyptor (Schilliger, 2024), run on flattened scroll-segmentation outputs. General-purpose
 77 volume renderers (ParaView, 3-D Slicer) render the raw scalar field per voxel without surface-
 78 aware abstractions. Our pipeline consumes the surface-volume output of VC3D/Thaumato and
 79 operates one stage downstream, on the per-feature volumetric cubes into which that surface is
 80 recast.

81

3. Data

82 Data used in the preparation of this article were obtained from the *Vesuvius Challenge – CT*
 83 *Scans of Herculaneum Papyri* (Angelotti et al., 2025), building on the EduceLab-Scrolls effort (Par-
 84 sons et al., 2023). We work specifically with the *Scroll 5* (PHerc. 172) segment 20241108120732,
 85 distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 (CC BY-NC 4.0) li-
 86 cense (Vesuvius Challenge, 2025b).

87 The flattened layer stack was produced by the *Thaumato Anakalyptor* virtual-unwrapping
 88 pipeline of Schilliger (Schilliger, 2024), which fits a sheet through the μ CT volume and re-samples
 89 it as a stack of co-registered depth slices. After virtual unwrapping the segment is rendered as
 90 a stack of 65 co-registered depth layers, each a single-channel 8-bit image of size 4771×7414

91 pixels. Layer index $\ell \in \{0, \dots, 64\}$ runs from the shallow side of the papyrus surface through the
 92 substrate to the deep side.

93 A finer point shapes every depth-axis interpretation in the rest of the paper. The Thaumato
 94 pipeline tiles the raw μ CT volume into 3-D *Grid Cells* of 500^3 voxels, extracts a surface PointCloud,
 95 partitions it into local sheet patches with Mask3D (Schult et al., 2023), and resolves the global
 96 sheet topology through a custom Random-Walk procedure over an overlap-weighted patch
 97 graph, propagating per-patch winding numbers from a seed patch (Schilliger, 2024). One con-
 98 sequence follows: the depth axis ℓ is a normal-coordinate sample along the inferred sheet, not a
 99 physical μ CT z , so layer-to-layer geometry is locally Euclidean but globally curved. Alongside the
 100 depth stack, the segment ships with a *composite.jpg* image, a single-channel max-projection
 101 composite over the depth stack, released alongside the segment (Angelotti et al., 2025) as a 2-D
 102 orientation view of the unwrapped sheet. The representative data are depicted in Fig. 3.

Figure 3 – Three views of segment 20241108120732 as released by the Vesuvius Challenge (Angelotti et al., 2025). Left: depth layer $\ell = 32$ in its native orientation. Centre: the segment’s *composite.jpg*. Right: reference ink prediction (inverted, bright = predicted ink) with the 25 manually located 512×512 glyph crops overlaid as red boxes. CT-background pixels of the left and centre panels are painted white for legibility on the page.

103 For quantitative evaluation we use 25 single-glyph crops of Scroll 5. The Greek-letter as-
 104 signment of each crop is approximate, based on our best reading of the reference prediction,
 105 and serves only as a convenience label. The reference ink evidence for the entire segment²
 106 is the prediction file (4864×7424 px), released by the Vesuvius Challenge alongside the seg-
 107 ment. The depth layers themselves are stored at 4771×7414 px, so the prediction has a small
 108 $\sim 93 \times 10$ px padding overshoot that we trim before re-sampling the prediction onto the layer grid
 109 by nearest-neighbour interpolation. Per-glyph 512×512 binary masks are then cropped out of
 110 the re-sampled prediction at manually recorded (x, y) offsets. No part of the dataset is split into
 111 training/validation/test sets because the pipeline contains no trainable parameters; the entire
 112 dataset is used at evaluation time.

²<https://dl.ash2txt.org/full-scrolls/Scroll15/PHerc172.volpkg/paths/20241108120732/>

4. Methodology

113

114 We characterise the per-layer ink/papyrus separability of the corpus, evaluate each 3-D tex-
 115 ture descriptor individually, and combine them into a deterministic ink-detection chain (depth
 116 prior, adaptive threshold, fusion).

4.1. Pixel intensity distributions: ink vs. papyrus

117 The supervised community prediction (Section 3) collapses the 65-layer parallelepiped to a
 118 single 2-D map; pooled across the 25 specimens the ink/papyrus contrast is concentrated near
 119 the centre and vanishes at the slab boundaries (Fig. 4, Table 1). We quantify separability per layer
 120 by the standardised mean gap d' and the ℓ_1 -overlap \mathcal{O}_{L_1} between the two pooled densities $\hat{p}_{p,\ell}$
 121 and $\hat{p}_{i,\ell}$,

$$(1) \quad d'(\ell) = \frac{|\mu_i(\ell) - \mu_p(\ell)|}{\sigma_{\text{pool}}(\ell)}, \quad \sigma_{\text{pool}}(\ell) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}(\sigma_i(\ell)^2 + \sigma_p(\ell)^2)}, \quad \mathcal{O}_{L_1}(\ell) = \sum_{b=0}^{255} \min(\hat{p}_{p,\ell}(b), \hat{p}_{i,\ell}(b)).$$

122
 123 A narrow band of central layers around the peak at $\ell = 31$ carries the visible separation
 124 ($d' > 0.3$ for $\ell \in [27, 32]$; peak $d'(31) = 0.42$, $\mathcal{O}_{L_1}(31) = 0.79$, mean gap $\Delta\mu(\ell) = |\mu_i(\ell) - \mu_p(\ell)| = 11.4$
 125 grey levels at $\ell = 31$). At the shallow side and deep boundaries the gap collapses ($\Delta\mu(0) =$
 126 1.9 , $\Delta\mu(64) = 0.6$), d' contracts by 5–17 \times and \mathcal{O}_{L_1} saturates above 0.96. Equivalently, the non-
 127 overlapping mass $1 - \mathcal{O}_{L_1}$ drops from 21% at the centre to 3–4% at the surfaces – statistically
 128 indistinguishable for any practical intensity threshold. The supervised ground truth therefore
 129 describes ink only as it appears near the central layer.

Figure 4 – Pooled pixel-intensity densities at the centre depth $\ell = 31$ for ink (orange, dashed) and papyrus (blue), averaged over the 25 annotated specimens. The visible ink lobe of this layer flattens into the papyrus mode at the surfaces (Table 1).

130 The ink-detection techniques therefore must (i) operate on layers where the ink signal is ac-
 131 tually present and (ii) zero its support elsewhere; the peak-anchored normal prior of Section 4.3
 132 is exactly this per-specimen restriction.

ℓ	...	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	...
μ_p	...	146.9	149.2	151.9	155.1	158.2	160.8	162.2	162.0	160.2	157.1	153.3	149.7	146.8	144.9	144.3	144.5	145.2	146.1	146.8	...
μ_i	...	151.0	153.8	157.3	161.2	165.4	169.3	172.0	172.9	171.6	168.2	163.1	157.5	152.7	149.2	147.5	147.1	147.6	148.5	149.3	...
d'	...	0.173	0.190	0.214	0.243	0.284	0.337	0.387	0.420	0.422	0.395	0.343	0.279	0.218	0.166	0.130	0.109	0.103	0.103	0.105	...
\mathcal{O}_{L_1}	...	0.926	0.921	0.910	0.893	0.872	0.843	0.815	0.793	0.787	0.805	0.832	0.862	0.888	0.908	0.923	0.932	0.936	0.936	0.940	...

Table 1 – Per-layer ink/papyrus separation across the central depth window $\ell \in [23, 41]$, pooled over 25 specimens, according to definitions in Eq. (1).

133 4.2. Ink sources across volume

134 An unwrapped Herculanum segment is rarely a single flat sheet: the Thaumato stitching pro-
 135 cedure assembles volume chunks that can include the recto face, the verso face directly above
 136 or below it, and bleed-through from neighbouring windings. Each of those physical surfaces sits
 137 at a different depth inside the 65-layer "cube" and constitutes a distinct plausible *source of ink-*
 138 *shaped evidence*.

Figure 5 – Per-letter XZ cross-section collage for 1-pi. *Left*: the segment-mean curve $\mu(z)$ (red) and per-layer variance $\sigma^2(z)$ (teal) on twin axes; detected cluster centres drawn as magenta verticals with their z label. *Right*: raw μ CT cross-sections of the 512×65 X-by-Z slab at Y-stride 32 (16 panels, turbo colourmap, pixel intensity floored at 1). Ticks above each panel mark the detected cluster centres. The dominant central cluster ($z^* = 29$) sits at the peak of $\mu(z)$; the two flanking clusters ($z = 14$ and $z = 49$) correspond to other pieces of papyrus visible as faint bright stripes.

139 For 1-pi, three clusters at $z = 14$, $z = 29$ and $z = 49$ line up with the faint curved bright stripes,
 140 visible in the raw XZ cross-sections (Fig. 5). Each sheet must be treated as a separate candidate
 141 depth window, operating voxelwise on the full cube and then choosing one source per specimen
 142 or region; this is done according to the depth-prior construction outlined in Section 4.3. Across
 143 the 25 specimens the peak detector finds one surface in 7 cases, two in 13 and three in 5.

144 4.3. Peak-anchored normal depth prior

145 The prior is derived from the raw μ CT volume $I \in \{0, \dots, 255\}^{D \times H \times W}$; the depth weight it
 146 produces is then applied to whichever feature volume is being projected. The intuition is simple:
 147 the prior is re-centred on the layer at which the raw slab's intensity is at the same time strongest
 148 and most spatially coherent, and clipped to the surrounding mean-curve dip so it does not bleed
 149 into neighbouring sheets.

150 Concretely, for each layer z we form the min-max normalised layer mean

$$(2) \quad \tilde{\mu}_z = \frac{\mu_z - \min_z \mu_z}{\max_z \mu_z - \min_z \mu_z}, \quad \mu_z = \frac{1}{HW} \sum_{x,y} I(x, y, z),$$

151 together with the standard von Neumann 4-neighbour coherence c_z defined on the indicator of
 152 the per-layer 75-th percentile, and pick the coherence-weighted argmax

$$(3) \quad \ell_0 = \arg \max_z \tilde{\mu}_z \cdot c_z.$$

153 The support interval $[z_L, z_R]$ is read off the layer-mean curve as the nearest local minima on
 154 either side of ℓ_0 (extended to the cube boundaries when no interior minimum exists), and the
 155 symmetric normal envelope

$$(4) \quad w(z) = \exp(-(z - \ell_0)^2 / (2\sigma^2)) \cdot \mathbb{1}[z_L \leq z \leq z_R], \quad \sigma = 15,$$

156 is the depth weight. The indicator zeros w outside the support interval, so the normal envelope
 157 centred at ℓ_0 contributes only inside the mean-curve dip. The dispersion $\sigma = 15$ is intentionally
 158 larger than the typical peak half-width on the corpus, so that the per-specimen support interval
 159 $[z_L, z_R]$ carries the depth selection, and the Gaussian only smoothly tapers the weight near the
 160 bracket edges. Algorithm 1 summarises the procedure.

Algorithm 1 Peak-anchored normal depth prior (per specimen).

Require: raw μ CT volume $I \in \{0, \dots, 255\}^{D \times H \times W}$, dispersion parameter σ

Ensure: depth weights $\{w_z\}_{z=0}^{D-1}$, centre ℓ_0 , support interval $[z_L, z_R]$

- 1: $\mu_z \leftarrow \frac{1}{HW} \sum_{x,y} I(x, y, z)$
 - 2: $q_z \leftarrow$ 75-th percentile of $I(\cdot, \cdot, z)$; $A_z \leftarrow \mathbb{K}[I(\cdot, \cdot, z) > q_z]$
 - 3: $c_z \leftarrow$ 4-neighbour pair density of A_z
 - 4: $\tilde{\mu}_z \leftarrow (\mu_z - \min_z \mu_z) / \max(\max_z \mu_z - \min_z \mu_z, \epsilon)$
 - 5: $\ell_0 \leftarrow \arg \max_z \tilde{\mu}_z \cdot c_z$
 - 6: $z_L \leftarrow$ largest $i < \ell_0$ with $\mu_i \leq \mu_{i \pm 1}$ (else 0)
 - 7: $z_R \leftarrow$ smallest $i > \ell_0$ with $\mu_i \leq \mu_{i \pm 1}$ (else $D-1$)
 - 8: $w_z \leftarrow \exp(-(z - \ell_0)^2 / (2\sigma^2)) \cdot \mathbb{K}[z_L \leq z \leq z_R]$
 - 9: **return** $\{w_z\}, \ell_0, z_L, z_R$
-

161 For multi-sheet specimens (Section 4.2) the single-peak $\arg \max$ of Eq. (3) generalises in the
 162 implementation to a prominence-filtered set of peaks of the same profile $\tilde{\mu}_z \cdot c_z$. Only the highest-
 163 prominence peak is used from that set; secondary peaks are not consumed and are reported as
 164 audit candidates.

165 4.4. Volumetric texture descriptors

166 We define three texture descriptors that act on the
 167 volumetric μ CT cube directly, in 3-D, so the pixel values'
 168 co-variation along z and the spatial coherence of an ink
 169 stroke across consecutive layers enter the operator re-
 170 sponse inside its own support. Per-layer 2-D analogues
 171 of the same operators run on the projected output, not
 172 on the voxel grid, and are therefore outside the scope
 173 of this volumetric study.

174 Acting in 3-D gives direct access to fibre orientation,
 175 stroke-thickness variation across z , and the spatial dis-
 176 tribution of anomalous-intensity voxels inside the slab
 177 (Fig. 6); the 2-D-projected per-operator panels of Fig. 7
 178 preserve the magnitude of the response but flatten
 179 its spatial alignment along z . Ground-truth ink masks
 180 for this corpus are, however, supplied only in 2-D, so
 181 any quantitative evaluation against them requires a 2-D
 182 projection of the volumetric prediction and a binaris-
 183 ation step before per-pixel MCC can be computed; Sec-
 184 tions 4.5 and 4.6 define that threshold and projection.

Figure 6 – $3\text{-}\beta$ slab, 3-D block autocorrelation ($b=2$) above $T = 155$.

185 Throughout this section $I \in \{0, \dots, 255\}^{D \times H \times W}$ denotes the single-channel 8-bit μ CT slab
 186 and F_{3D} a generic 3-D feature volume of the same shape. Fig. 7 shows the per-operator response
 187 on a representative specimen (compared to the raw z -mean) collapsed to 2-D.

Figure 7 – Per-voxel response of the three 3-D texture operators on specimen 10- γ , 2-D-projected and shown next to the raw-intensity baseline. (a) Raw μ CT z -mean under the same projection; (b) $ACF_{b=2}^{3D}$; (c) FOS^{3D} ($w=5$); (d) LTE_{LL}^{3D} ($k=7$). All panels use the per-specimen peak-anchored normal projection of Section 4.3 ($\ell_0=30$, $\sigma=15$, support interval $[21, 38]$), jet-mapped after 2-98% percentile clipping (blue \rightarrow red as evidence rises).

188 4.4.1. 3-D autocorrelation. The 3-D block-based autocorrelation function (ACF) tiles the cube
 189 into disjoint $b \times b \times b$ blocks and, for every offset $(k, l, m) \in [0, b]^3$, computes a per-block circular
 190 autocorrelation: each block is multiplied element-wise by the copy of itself shifted by (k, l, m)
 191 with wrap-around at the *block* boundary, and the resulting scalar is stored back at the in-block
 192 position (k, l, m) . For a block B with corner $\mathbf{x}_B = (z_B, y_B, x_B)$,

$$(5) \quad ACF_b^{3D}(B; k, l, m) = \frac{1}{b^3} \sum_{\mathbf{d} \in [0, b]^3} I(\mathbf{x}_B + \mathbf{d}) I(\mathbf{x}_B + ((\mathbf{d} + (k, l, m)) \bmod b)), \quad 0 \leq k, l, m < b,$$

193 where $\bmod b$ is applied componentwise. Each b^3 block thus reports its own internal correlation
 194 structure. We use $b=2$ exclusively: it probes the $\Delta z=1$ inter-layer lag – the immediate continu-
 195 ity that distinguishes an ink fibre from acquisition noise – without averaging ink-and-substrate
 196 together inside the same block, which is what happens at larger b once the block straddles the
 197 full ~ 3 -voxel stroke thickness.

198 4.4.2. 3-D first-order statistics. The first-order-statistics (FOS) energy is the local mean of the
 199 squared signal over a $w \times w$ window. With the slab rescaled to $\tilde{I} = I/255 \in [0, 1]$ for numerical
 200 stability, the volumetric counterpart on a box of side w is

$$(6) \quad FOS_{3D}(x, y, z) = \frac{1}{w^3} \sum_{(i, j, k) \in B_w(x, y, z)} \tilde{I}(i, j, k)^2,$$

201 where $B_w(x, y, z) \subset \mathbb{Z}^3$ is the $w \times w \times w$ voxel box centred on (x, y, z) . We use $w=5$: the 3-D box
 202 averages out small CT noise without erasing the strokes, which are typically 3-6 layers thick.

203 4.4.3. 3-D Laws texture energy. The 3-D Laws texture energy (LTE) on the $L \otimes L \otimes L$ kernel (LTE_{LL}^{3D}
 204 henceforth) is the triple outer product of the length- k binomial smoothing kernel L_k (for $k=7$,
 205 $L_7 = (1, 6, 15, 20, 15, 6, 1)$):

$$(7) \quad K_{LLL}(i, j, m) = L_k(i) L_k(j) L_k(m), \quad i, j, m \in \{0, \dots, k-1\},$$

206 which we convolve with the (normalised) volume I and whose absolute response is reported.
 207 $k=7$ is the smallest odd length that captures three full intra-stroke layers on each side of a voxel.
 208 The isotropic 3-D kernel responds to ink strokes whose energy is distributed across several depth
 209 layers.

210 4.5. Adaptive threshold

211 The fused prediction \hat{I}_s (Section 4.6) drifts from specimen to specimen, so a fixed cut-off at
 212 $T=128$ – the midpoint of the 8-bit intensity range $[0, 255]$ – over- or under-fires depending on
 213 the specimen. We binarise instead at the per-specimen offset

$$(8) \quad T_s = \mu(\hat{I}_s) + k \sigma(\hat{I}_s), \quad k = 0.5,$$

214 with $k=0.5$ chosen so the accepted-pixel fraction (22–28% on the empirically right-skewed pre-
 215 dictions) matches the observed per-crop ink coverage $|\overline{M_s}|/|s| = 0.27 \pm 0.07$.

216 A small fraction of pixels (pit edges, inclusion grains, surface damage, acquisition speckle) sit
 217 far above the prediction's upper tail and would bias $\mu(\hat{I}_s)$ and $\sigma(\hat{I}_s)$ upward if allowed into the pool.
 218 We strip them with a one-dimensional Reed–Xiaoli (RX) anomaly filter – a scalar Mahalanobis
 219 distance from the prediction mean,

$$(9) \quad z(x, y) = |\hat{I}_s(x, y) - \mu(\hat{I}_s)| / \sigma(\hat{I}_s),$$

220 – and recompute T_s on the pixels whose RX score is at or below the 99-th percentile Q_{99} of z :

$$(10) \quad T_s = \mu(\hat{I}_s, K_{RX}) + 0.5 \sigma(\hat{I}_s, K_{RX}), \quad K_{RX} = \{(x, y) : z(x, y) \leq Q_{99}\}.$$

221 The trim removes the bright micro-specks without ever masking the classifier itself: T_s is com-
 222 puted on K_{RX} but the binarisation rule $\hat{I}_s \geq T_s$ is applied to every pixel of the prediction.

223 4.6. Volumetric Fusion

224 Each operator captures a different aspect of the local stroke signal (energy, low-pass smooth-
 225 ness disturbance, short-range z -coherence); a per-voxel mean fusion exploits this complemen-
 226 tarity by averaging the three feature volumes after min–max normalisation, in order to intensify
 227 potential ink/papyri dissimilarity:

$$(11) \quad F_{3D}(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{3}[\widetilde{FOS}_{3D}(\mathbf{x}) + \widetilde{LTE}_{3D,LL}(\mathbf{x}) + \widetilde{ACF}_{b=2}^{3D}(\mathbf{x})], \quad \tilde{X}(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{X(\mathbf{x}) - \min X}{\max X - \min X}.$$

228 The fused volume is projected to 2-D by the per-column maximum of the depth-weighted
 229 response,

$$(12) \quad \hat{I}_s(x, y) = \max_z F_{3D}(x, y, z) w(z),$$

230 with $w(z)$ the peak-anchored Gaussian envelope of Section 4.3; the result is smoothed by ten it-
 231 erations of a soft Markov-random-field (MRF) posterior smoother (closed-form per-step iterated-
 232 conditional-modes (ICM) update on a Gaussian MRF with a quadratic smoothness prior (Besag,
 233 1986), $\beta=2.5$, 4-connected) and binarised at T_s . Figure 8 summarises the end-to-end chain.

234

5. Evaluation

235 We benchmark each individual 3-D operator and the three-operator fusion against the 25
 236 supervised reference masks of Section 3. The protocol below fixes the evaluation metric and

Figure 8 – End-to-end 3-D pipeline: raw μ CT cube \rightarrow three volumetric texture descriptors \rightarrow per-voxel mean fusion \rightarrow peak-anchored normal depth projection \rightarrow soft MRF posterior smoother \rightarrow adaptive threshold T_s .

237 the boundary-handling convention; the headline result and a sensitivity sweep over the buffer
238 width follow.

239 5.1. Protocol

240 For every specimen s we compare the thresholded fused score \hat{I}_s to the manual mask M_s , both
241 co-registered at layer-stack resolution. Pixels within $\delta = 4$ px of any ground-truth (GT) contour
242 (outer letter boundary *and* interior holes, e.g. the loops of β , ρ , α , δ) are excluded; the choice of δ
243 is motivated and swept in Section 5.3. Hole pixels themselves are treated as background ground
244 truth: a positive prediction inside a β -loop counts as a false positive. The headline metric is the
245 Matthews correlation coefficient (Matthews, 1975), robust to ink/non-ink imbalance and zero
246 for random noise.

247 5.2. Headline result

248 Across the 25 annotated Greek-letter specimens the mean MCC of the 3-operator stack of
249 Eq. (11) is $\text{MCC} = +0.3643$ (median $+0.3861$, top $+0.523$ on $17\text{-}\eta$). Among the individual descrip-
250 tors, $\text{ACF}_{b=2}^{3D}$ is the strongest single operator on the corpus (mean $+0.3743$, median $+0.3917$) and
251 on its own even narrowly outperforms the three-operator fusion – both mean and median best
252 each specimen-by-specimen comparison fall to it in $16/25$ specimens (Table 2). Per-specimen
253 glyph predictions are visualised across the full corpus in Fig. 9.

254 5.3. Boundary buffer sensitivity

255 The buffer width $\delta = 4$ px is picked *a priori* to absorb the small residual contour uncertainty
256 of the supervised reference masks (which are themselves per-pixel network predictions and are
257 unlikely to be pixel-perfect along the ink stroke) plus Thaumato’s trilinear-interpolation sampling
258 error (Schilliger, 2024). To verify that the headline number is not an artefact of that choice we
259 sweep $\delta \in \{0, 2, 4, 8, 12\}$ px under the otherwise unchanged headline pipeline (Table 3).

Table 2 – Per-specimen MCC of each individual 3-D operator and the 3-operator fusion under the headline pipeline of Section 5.1 (each column runs the same projection + MRF + adaptive T_s pipeline with its own input volume; T_s column reports the fusion threshold). Sorted by descending fusion MCC.

Specimen	FOS ^{3D}		LTE ^{3D} _{LL}		ACF ^{3D} _{b=2}		Fusion	
	MCC	T_s	MCC	T_s	MCC	T_s	MCC	T_s
7- η	+0.490	85.8	+0.510	109.6	+0.533	103.5	+0.515	99.0
17- η	+0.500	96.3	+0.521	119.6	+0.522	110.1	+0.523	109.2
8- τ	+0.443	86.1	+0.452	109.4	+0.476	103.1	+0.458	98.6
9- ν	+0.453	86.3	+0.463	110.3	+0.472	103.7	+0.465	99.6
18- σ	+0.384	93.6	+0.414	118.4	+0.450	113.4	+0.422	107.6
20- ν	+0.448	102.4	+0.442	126.4	+0.441	116.0	+0.444	114.8
10- γ	+0.425	100.2	+0.440	121.4	+0.447	110.9	+0.441	110.4
15- ν	+0.440	91.0	+0.445	115.3	+0.436	102.7	+0.442	102.8
3- β	+0.415	89.3	+0.430	111.4	+0.442	97.2	+0.432	100.1
11- χ	+0.389	89.1	+0.410	113.1	+0.427	101.0	+0.412	102.1
21- δ	+0.355	88.5	+0.383	117.7	+0.411	107.4	+0.386	106.6
16- ρ	+0.404	91.5	+0.399	116.9	+0.391	108.9	+0.401	105.6
1- π	+0.395	91.9	+0.395	111.7	+0.397	99.5	+0.398	101.9
2- κ	+0.356	104.8	+0.378	123.4	+0.392	104.9	+0.377	110.9
19- σ	+0.377	107.0	+0.370	130.1	+0.378	119.4	+0.373	120.0
14- ω	+0.339	105.0	+0.347	124.5	+0.363	101.3	+0.351	111.2
25- π	+0.318	93.6	+0.335	114.3	+0.349	94.5	+0.336	102.8
13- μ	+0.297	88.9	+0.292	114.1	+0.328	107.9	+0.304	102.1
4- λ	+0.294	75.2	+0.323	97.1	+0.326	89.1	+0.320	86.5
24- δ	+0.298	98.8	+0.287	120.1	+0.275	110.3	+0.288	109.4
5- α	+0.230	80.2	+0.242	105.5	+0.254	96.3	+0.244	95.9
22- ι	+0.186	96.9	+0.202	123.2	+0.248	111.4	+0.210	111.3
12- λ	+0.195	83.5	+0.208	108.5	+0.224	101.4	+0.211	97.4
23- α	+0.182	93.3	+0.194	117.3	+0.217	108.9	+0.198	106.3
6- β	+0.155	86.6	+0.152	108.8	+0.159	98.4	+0.156	97.3
Mean	+0.351	92.2	+0.361	115.5	+0.374	104.9	+0.364	104.4
Median	+0.377	91.5	+0.383	115.3	+0.392	103.7	+0.386	102.8

260 The dependence is monotone: removing the buffer entirely penalises the model for the resid-
 261 ual stroke-shape mismatch of the reference mask and costs ~ 0.02 on the mean; widening the
 262 buffer to 12 px gains ~ 0.03 but pushes the model towards losing its physical anchor.

δ (px)	Fusion mean MCC	Fusion median MCC
0	+0.3421	+0.3604
2	+0.3537	+0.3728
4	+0.3643	+0.3889
8	+0.3813	+0.4117
12	+0.3926	+0.4324

Table 3 – Boundary-buffer sensitivity of the headline Fusion MCC across the 25 specimens. Headline pipeline of Section 5.2 held fixed; only δ varied.

Figure 9 – 5×5 collage of the 25 specimens, each tile showing the binarised prediction $\hat{I}_s \geq T_s$ of the *best-performing* method for that specimen across $\{\text{FOS}^{3\text{D}}, \text{LTE}_{LL}^{3\text{D}}, \text{ACF}_{b=2}^{3\text{D}}, \text{Fusion}\}$ (per-row winner of Table 2), sorted by descending best MCC. Each tile is shown inverted (black = predicted ink, white = background) with the manual ink-mask contour overlaid in red (1 px) and the $\delta = 4$ boundary band overlaid in semi-transparent bright yellow.

263

6. Ablations

264

265

266

The headline of Section 5.2 owes its number to two ingredients acting together: the three 3-D operators and the per-specimen peak-anchored normal depth prior that selects which layers they speak from. Beyond the 512×512 glyph crops on which it is calibrated, the per-specimen prior

267 is not guaranteed to remain as effective at the segment scale: a full Thaumato segment spans a
 268 much wider range of papyrus-surface topology – locally varying sheet orientation, multiple over-
 269 and under-lapping wraps, and stitching artefacts (Section 3) – and the mean-curve peak that
 270 anchors the prior on a clean glyph is no longer the dominant signal across such a heterogeneous
 271 region. To stress-test that limitation we keep $ACF_{b=2}^{3D}$ – the strongest single operator on the
 272 corpus (Table 2) – and replace the prior with a uniform per-column maximum inside a manually
 273 chosen depth window (shallow [0, 20], middle [21, 43], deep [44, 64], covering all 65 layers without
 274 overlap).

Figure 10 – $ACF_{b=2}^{3D}$ grayscale prediction on the full 4771×7414 segment under three contiguous depth bands.

275 Figures 10 and 11 visualise the resulting full-segment $ACF_{b=2}^{3D}$ predictions in grayscale and
 276 jet. The middle band recovers the substrate slab around the nominal ink layer $\ell \approx 31$; the shal-
 277 low and deep bands expose ink-shaped responses on over- and under-lapping sheets that the
 278 headline’s central support interval correctly suppresses for per-letter benchmarking but which
 279 the community ink-prediction file – committed to a single depth window – cannot report.

280 Specifically, running the same $ACF_{b=2}^{3D}$ pipeline on a 3573×736 wide band across the shallow
 281 window $\ell \in [0, 21]$ of the segment surfaces a partially recognisable text fragment that does not
 282 belong to this segment prediction at all: it belongs to a neighbouring segment whose physical
 283 surface overlaps in the (x, y) plane but lives at a different depth along the unwrapped normal.
 284 The recognised letters match the community ink-prediction of *that* neighbouring segment, not
 285 of the segment whose volume actually produced the ACF response (Fig. 12). The community
 286 prediction of the segment we operate on contains no recognisable symbols in this region.

287 7. Discussion

288 The headline result is the best-single-operator $MCC = 0.374$ across 25 Greek-letter speci-
 289 mens under the protocol of Section 5.1. $ACF_{b=2}^{3D}$ alone narrowly edges the three-operator fusion

Figure 11 – Jet panel of the same three $ACF_{b=2}^{3D}$ predictions above the per-band adaptive threshold. Several of the ink-shaped responses surfaced by the shallow and deep bands do not appear in the community ink-prediction file released alongside the segment.

Figure 12 – Top: $ACF_{b=2}^{3D}$ grayscale on $\ell \in [0, 21]$. Middle: the same in jet above the adaptive threshold. Bottom: matching spatial crop of the community prediction for neighbouring segment 20241108111522 (inverted, black = predicted ink).

290 (+0.364). The cross-band ablation of Fig. 11 shows that ink-shaped evidence still surfaces with
 291 the depth prior disabled, isolating the operator-level contribution from the prior.

292 **Letter shapes differ from neural-network predictions.** The reference contours of Fig. 9 come
 293 from a supervised network prediction, not from manual letter traces. The deterministic panels
 294 recover the contoured letter *region* but rarely the exact *shape* pixel-for-pixel: on clean specimens
 295 our strokes are sharper or thinner than the network contour, on others the surfaced ink falls
 296 slightly outside it; in some cases (e.g. 16- ρ) the network prediction itself overlaps actual void
 297 (damaged region) inside the contoured area, so it is not a per-pixel-MCC-optimal target; this is
 298 consistent with the supervised network fitting its predictions to canonical Greek-letter shapes
 299 rather than to per-voxel ink evidence alone. Section 5.3 quantifies the mismatch.

300 **Cost of the 2-D projection.** The per-column max projection of Eq. 12 retains stroke magnitude
 301 but discards the per-voxel z-alignment, conflating ink-bearing fibres with off-surface anomalous
 302 voxels at the same (x, y) ; the MCC against 2-D masks therefore underestimates the volumetric
 303 evidence the descriptors actually recover.

304 **Where the method still fails.** The lower-tail specimens of Table 2 – 4- λ , 22- ι , 24- δ , 12- λ , 23- α ,
 305 6- β – coincide with locally deformed substrate; the operators recover only the parts of the letter
 306 that lie on intact papyrus, being prone to capturing noise.

307 **Cross-segment and cross-scroll transfer.** Within Scroll 5 (PHerc. 172) the pipeline transfers
 308 without re-tuning and locates the silhouettes of glyphs already present in the community ink-
 309 prediction across a diverse set of segments. Applied to Scroll 1 (PHerc. Paris 4) the same stack
 310 does not yield comparable results: only rare, fragmentary parts of the predicted silhouettes ap-
 311 pear, almost exclusively at the ink/papyrus boundary. We treat the Scroll 1 outcome as a negative
 312 result. The pipeline is therefore positioned as an exploratory, complementary signal – open to
 313 further refinement, not a universal Herculaneum papyri reader.

314 **Position relative to the open ink-detection sub-challenges.** Returning to the open ink-detection
 315 agenda (Vesuvius Challenge, 2025a): the criterion of reverse-engineerable voxel-level patterns
 316 is met by construction – the pipeline is composed exclusively of closed-form descriptors, a de-
 317 terministic depth prior and a soft MRF posterior smoother. Whole-segment application is exer-
 318 cised by the three-band experiment of Section 6, which scales to the full 4771×7414 flattened
 319 sheet without per-spec retuning. The training-free evidence-map criterion is addressed indirectly
 320 through the deterministic per-pixel signal that a supervised pipeline can consume as an additional
 321 input or as a weak label. Absolute model performance is the one open-agenda criterion this work
 322 does *not* attempt to solve in isolation.

323

8. Limitations and future work

324 The headline result notwithstanding, the present unsupervised pipeline carries several ac-
 325 knowledged drawbacks, discussed below alongside the future-work directions they motivate.

326 **Single scroll.** As reported above, the pipeline was evaluated on multiple segments of Scroll 5
 327 (PHerc. 172), where it attained moderately strong results conditional on the quality of the up-
 328 stream segmentation, and on several segments of Scroll 1 (PHerc. Paris 4), where its performance
 329 degraded extremely. Behaviour on the remaining Herculaneum scrolls is unknown, so the gener-
 330 ality of the approach cannot be assessed without further experiments.

331 **Narrow feature stack.** The fusion uses three volumetric descriptors. Beyond multi-resolution 3-
 332 D Laws kernels and ACF block sizes outside the tested $b=2$, other volumetric texture families –
 333 3-D Gabor filters, 3-D local binary patterns, 3-D causal autoregressive (CAR) predictive-surprise

334 volumes, structure-tensor descriptors and learned-dictionary responses — are natural candidates
335 worth trying to analyze the volumetric ink signal from different perspectives.

336 **Pre-segmentation application.** The descriptors act on voxel patterns directly, with no depen-
337 dence on a virtual-unwrapping step. Running the pipeline on the raw μ CT "unwrapped" vol-
338 ume, before segmentation, may surface ink-shaped evidence that informs the segmentation it-
339 self rather than consuming its output.

340 **Substrate-failure recovery.** Specimens on locally deformed substrate lose recall in proportion
341 to substrate damage. A finer-grained substrate reconstruction — e.g. a polynomial sheet fit per
342 detected papyrus surface — could make this damage explicit and tolerable.

343 **Ink/fibre disentanglement.** The present descriptors respond to papyrus fibres as well as to ink
344 traces; separating the two responses is a clear direction for future work.

345 **Hybrid supervised priors.** The fused 3-D volume and the per-band predictions are per-voxel sig-
346 nals available *before* any thresholding step. Conditioning a supervised network on those signals
347 instead of the raw layer stack is the quite interesting possibility for hybridisation.

348 9. Conclusions

349 We presented a fully unsupervised, deterministic, label-free volumetric ink-detection pipeline
350 for μ CT-imaged Herculaneum papyri. Three contributions support the headline result:

351 (1) Three volumetric texture descriptors — 3-D first-order energy, 3-D Laws LL energy and
352 3-D block autocorrelation at $b=2$ — that act jointly along the depth axis inside their own
353 support.

354 (2) A peak-anchored normal depth prior whose centre is the coherence-weighted argmax
355 of the *fused* volume and whose support is clipped to the surrounding mean-curve local
356 minima, replacing a population-average ink layer with a per-specimen one.

357 (3) A per-specimen adaptive threshold $T_s = \mu(\hat{l}_s) + 0.5 \sigma(\hat{l}_s)$ computed on the prediction's
358 own intensity distribution after a Reed–Xiaoli 1% outlier trim.

359 Across 25 Scroll 5 (PHerc. 172) specimens, $ACF_{b=2}^{3D}$ leads at mean $MCC = +0.374$ (top $+0.533$
360 on $7-\eta$); the three-operator fusion follows at $+0.364$. On the full segment across shallow, middle
361 and deep depth bands, the same operator surfaces partially recognisable text matching the com-
362 munity ink-prediction of a neighbouring, overlapping segment. This deterministic, training-free
363 per-voxel evidence map can serve supervised detectors as an explainable auxiliary input or weak
364 label, and as a reproducible baseline for future Herculaneum ink-detection work.

365 10. Acknowledgements

366 The authors thank the Vesuvius Challenge community and the Educelab-Scrolls team for re-
367 leasing the μ CT data of Scroll 5 (PHerc. 172) (Angelotti et al., 2025; Parsons et al., 2023) under
368 CC BY-NC 4.0 (Vesuvius Challenge, 2025b), on which our experiments are run, and the Faculty
369 of Information Technology of the Czech Technical University in Prague and the Institute of Infor-
370 mation Theory and Automation of the Czech Academy of Sciences for institutional support.

371 11. Funding

372 The first author received only the standard doctoral stipend for full-time PhD students from
373 the Czech Technical University in Prague, Faculty of Information Technology. No external project
374 funding was used for the specific work reported here.

12. Conflict of interest disclosure

The authors declare no financial conflicts of interest in relation to the content of the article.

13. Author contributions (CRediT)

O. Korotetskyi: Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review and editing, Visualization.

M. Haindl: Conceptualization, Project administration, Theoretical guidance and advisory input, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

14. Use of generative AI

The authors disclose that large language models (specifically, the Claude family of models from Anthropic) were used as drafting assistants for translation, LaTeX formatting, and for code review during the development of the accompanying software. All AI-generated text, code, and equations were verified by the authors against source data and the underlying scripts before inclusion; no figures, photographs, or illustrations in this article were generated by AI. No bibliographic references were sourced from AI without independent verification of the DOI and the cited claim. The authors take full responsibility for the content of the article.

15. Data, script, code, and supplementary information availability

Scripts, code, configuration files, supplementary information, images and per-specimen output archives are available at <https://github.com/korotole/vtfid> and <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20766169> (Korotetskyi & Haindl, 2026). The data related to Scroll 5 / PHerc. 172 are released by the Vesuvius Challenge as part of the Educelab-Scrolls dataset (Parsons et al., 2023) under CC BY-NC 4.0; access via <https://scrollprize.org/data> (Vesuvius Challenge, 2025b).

References

- Angelotti G, Parsons S, Johnson S, Dal Prà ER, Rudolph J, Tafforeau P, Mirone A, Henderson P, Schilling H, McDonald F, Josey D, Nader Y, Parker CS, Seales WB (2025). Vesuvius Challenge – CT Scans of Herculaneum Papyri. Vesuvius Challenge. URL: <https://scrollprize.org/data>.
- Besag J (1986). On the Statistical Analysis of Dirty Pictures. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society. Series B (Methodological)* **48**, 259–302. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2517-6161.1986.tb01412.x>.
- Farritor L (2023). Vesuvius Challenge 2023 First Letters Prize: Technical Report. <https://scrollprize.org/firstletters>.
- Friedman N, Gross D, Seales WB (2023). Vesuvius Challenge 2023: First Letters and Grand Prize. <https://scrollprize.org/grandprize>.
- Friedman N, Gross D, Seales WB (2024). Vesuvius Challenge 2024 Prizes. https://scrollprize.org/2024_prizes.
- Handmer C, Friedman N, Gross D, Seales B, Vesuvius Challenge (2023). First Letters Found in New Scroll. Vesuvius Challenge – Substack. URL: <https://scrollprize.substack.com/p/first-letters-found-in-new-scroll>.

- 414 Haralick RM (1979). Statistical and Structural Approaches to Texture. *Proceedings of the IEEE* **67**,
415 786–804. <https://doi.org/10.1109/PROC.1979.11328>.
- 416 Haralick RM, Shanmugam K, Dinstein I (1973). Textural Features for Image Classification. *IEEE*
417 *Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics* **SMC-3**, 610–621. [https://doi.org/10.](https://doi.org/10.1109/TSMC.1973.4309314)
418 [1109/TSMC.1973.4309314](https://doi.org/10.1109/TSMC.1973.4309314).
- 419 Henderson P (2025). Virtually Unrolling the Herculaneum Papyri by Diffeomorphic Spiral Fitting.
420 arXiv:2512.04927. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2512.04927>.
- 421 Klenert N, Schwoerer F, Hajarolasvadi N, Bournez S, Arlt T, Mahnke HE, Lepper V, Baum D
422 (2025). Improving the Identification of Layers in 3-D Images of Ancient Papyrus Using Artifi-
423 cial Neural Networks. In: *2025 IEEE/CVF Winter Conference on Applications of Computer Vision*
424 *Workshops (WACVW)*. IEEE Computer Society, pp. 1204–1212. [https://doi.org/10.1109/](https://doi.org/10.1109/WACVW65960.2025.00143)
425 [WACVW65960.2025.00143](https://doi.org/10.1109/WACVW65960.2025.00143).
- 426 Kulagin P, Polevoy D, Chukalina M, Nikolaev D, Arlazarov VV (2024). Fully Automatic Virtual
427 Unwrapping Method for Documents Imaged by X-ray Tomography. In: *Document Analysis*
428 *and Recognition – ICDAR 2024*. Ed. by Elisa H. Barney Smith, Marcus Liwicki, and Liangrui
429 Peng. Vol. 14806. Lecture Notes in Computer Science. Cham: Springer, pp. 233–250. [https:](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-70543-4_14)
430 [//doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-70543-4_14](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-70543-4_14).
- 431 Laws KI (1980). Rapid Texture Identification. In: *Image Processing for Missile Guidance*. Vol. 0238.
432 Proceedings of SPIE, pp. 376–381. <https://doi.org/10.1117/12.959169>.
- 433 Mahnke HE, Arlt T, Baum D, Hege HC, Herter F, Lindow N, Manke I, Siopi T, Menei E, Etienne M,
434 Lepper V (2020). Virtual unfolding of folded papyri. *Journal of Cultural Heritage* **41**, 264–269.
435 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.culher.2019.07.007>.
- 436 Matthews BW (1975). Comparison of the predicted and observed secondary structure of T4
437 phage lysozyme. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA) – Protein Structure* **405**, 442–451. [https:](https://doi.org/10.1016/0005-2795(75)90109-9)
438 [//doi.org/10.1016/0005-2795\(75\)90109-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0005-2795(75)90109-9).
- 439 Mocella V, Brun E, Ferrero C, Delattre D (2015). Revealing letters in rolled Herculaneum papyri
440 by X-ray phase-contrast imaging. *Nature Communications* **6**, 5895. [https://doi.org/10.](https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms6895)
441 [1038/ncomms6895](https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms6895).
- 442 Nader Y (2023). Vesuvius Challenge 2023 First Letters Prize: Technical Report. [https://](https://scrollprize.org/firstletters)
443 scrollprize.org/firstletters.
- 444 Nader Y, Farritor L, Schilliger J (2024). Vesuvius Challenge 2023 Grand Prize: Winning Submis-
445 sion Code. <https://github.com/younader/Vesuvius-Grandprize-Winner>.
- 446 Parker S, EduceLab (2016). Volume Cartographer: Volumetric processing toolkit and C++ libraries
447 for the recovery and restoration of damaged cultural materials. [https://github.com/](https://github.com/educelab/volume-cartographer)
448 [educelab/volume-cartographer](https://github.com/educelab/volume-cartographer).
- 449 Parsons S, Parker CS, Chapman C, Mahmood M, Lazov S, Karchedi W, Caceres I, Casey S, Schilizzi
450 B, Salina H, Edmunds C, Mostler A, Schinault S, Hirvonen E, Hartman B, Liu X, Walker D, Tov
451 E, Seales WB (2023). EduceLab-Scrolls: Verifiable Recovery of Text from Herculaneum Papyri
452 using X-ray CT. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2304.02084*. [https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2304.](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2304.02084)
453 [02084](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2304.02084).
- 454 Polevoy D, Kulagin P, Ingacheva A, Soldatova Z, Chukalina M, Nikolaev D, Arlazarov VV (2022).
455 CT-OCR-2022. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7324269>.

- 456 Roth M, Nowak M (2025). Vesuvius Challenge First Title Prize: Recovering the Title of PHerc. 172
457 with a Custom MiniUNETR 3D Architecture. [https://github.com/mvrcii/vesuvius_](https://github.com/mvrcii/vesuvius_first_title_prize)
458 [first_title_prize](https://github.com/mvrcii/vesuvius_first_title_prize).
- 459 Schilliger J (2023). Crackle Viewer: A purpose-built tool for ink labelling and segment inspection
460 in Volume Cartographer outputs. <https://github.com/schillij95/Crackle-Viewer>.
- 461 Schilliger J (2024). Thaumato Anakalyptor: A 3-D virtual-unwrapping pipeline for the Hercu-
462 laneum papyri. Software, Vesuvius Challenge. URL: [https://github.com/schillij95/](https://github.com/schillij95/ThaumatoAnakalyptor)
463 [ThaumatoAnakalyptor](https://github.com/schillij95/ThaumatoAnakalyptor).
- 464 Schilling H, Johnson S, Vesuvius Challenge Team (2025). VC3D: OME-Zarr-enabled Volume Car-
465 tographer for Herculaneum papyri. [https://github.com/ScrollPrize/villa/tree/main/](https://github.com/ScrollPrize/villa/tree/main/volume-cartographer)
466 [volume-cartographer](https://github.com/ScrollPrize/villa/tree/main/volume-cartographer).
- 467 Schult J, Engelmann F, Hermans A, Litany O, Tang S, Leibe B (2023). Mask3D: Mask Transformer
468 for 3D Semantic Instance Segmentation. In: *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference*
469 *on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICRA48891.2023.10160590>.
- 470 Seales WB, Parker CS, Segal M, Tov E, Shor P, Porath Y (2016). From damage to discovery via
471 virtual unwrapping: Reading the scroll from En-Gedi. *Science Advances* **2**, e1601247. [https:](https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.1601247)
472 [//doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.1601247](https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.1601247).
- 473 Vesuvius Challenge (2025a). Tutorial: Ink Detection – Open Sub-Challenges. [https://](https://scrollprize.org/tutorial5)
474 scrollprize.org/tutorial5.
- 475 Vesuvius Challenge (2025b). Vesuvius Challenge – Data Access and Licensing. Online instruc-
476 tions for accessing the Educelab-Scrolls corpus, including PHerc. 172 (Scroll 5). URL: [https:](https://scrollprize.org/data)
477 [//scrollprize.org/data](https://scrollprize.org/data).
- 478 Vesuvius Challenge organizers (2023). Vesuvius Challenge – Surface Detection: Overview. Kag-
479 gle competition page. URL: [https://www.kaggle.com/competitions/vesuvius-](https://www.kaggle.com/competitions/vesuvius-challenge-surface-detection/overview)
480 [challenge-surface-detection/overview](https://www.kaggle.com/competitions/vesuvius-challenge-surface-detection/overview).
- 481 Vesuvius Challenge Team (2025). Exciting News from Scroll 5: Ink Detection and Segmentation
482 Progress on PHerc. 172. [https://scrollprize.substack.com/p/exciting-news-from-](https://scrollprize.substack.com/p/exciting-news-from-scroll-5)
483 [scroll-5](https://scrollprize.substack.com/p/exciting-news-from-scroll-5).
- 484 Vesuvius Challenge Team (2026). Approximately 70% of PHerc. 172 is Now Digitally Unwrapped.
485 <https://scrollprize.substack.com/p/70-of-pherc-172-is-now-digitally>.